

Studies in Geometrical Inversion. Part I. Resonance Reactions.

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P. Neogi, Chatterji and S. Neogi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 279) have shown that neither manganese dioxide nor sulphur dioxide alone produces inversion in maleic acid but by the united action of the two, inversion takes place very rapidly, the yield of fumaric acid being much greater than that obtained by Skraup using a mixture of sulphuretted hydrogen and sulphur dioxide solution.

In this paper their work has been confirmed with reference to maleic acid and extended to citraconic and other acids and esters of some geometrical isomers. Further, the reaction has been studied in all its bearing specially with reference to the effect of the products of the reaction on inversion, and the conclusion has become irresistible that the inversion actually takes place in the midst of the chemical reaction between sulphur dioxide and manganese dioxide and that a chemical reaction itself can act catalytically just as a catalytic substance would do. Such reactions as would take place *in the midst of* another chemical reaction have been called "resonance reactions."

EXPERIMENTAL.

Effect of the Action of Sulphur Dioxide and Manganese Dioxide on Geometrical Inversion.

Conversion of Maleic to Fumaric acid.—To maleic acid (1.7 g. in 5 c.c. of water) precipitated manganese dioxide (3.4 g.) was added. On passing sulphur dioxide through the above solution, the latter became clear, and the temperature rose to 70°. Within 3–4 minutes, a white precipitate rapidly separated. This was collected and extracted with absolute alcohol. The residue after removal of alcohol was dissolved in ether, from which colourless crystals of fumaric acid were obtained which sublimed at 200° (yield, 51 per cent.).

With a view to test whether the products of the reaction of sulphur dioxide on manganese dioxide suspended in water produce any inversion, sulphur dioxide was passed through precipitated manganese dioxide (4-5 g.) suspended in 25 c.c. of water until a clear solution was obtained. A solution of maleic acid in warm water was quickly added to the above clear liquid and the temperature was maintained at 60°-70° on a water-bath. Even after considerable time no separation of fumaric acid took place. The experiment was also repeated at 30° as well as at 100° with no better results. The mixed solution which smelt strongly of sulphur dioxide was kept overnight but no fumaric acid separated. This conclusively shows that the resultant products of the reaction of sulphur dioxide and manganese dioxide are in no way responsible for the conversion of maleic to fumaric acid.

Another variant tried was to suspend precipitated manganese dioxide in maleic acid solution and heat to 70°. On passing sulphur dioxide through the filtered solution, no fumaric acid separated even on cooling.

When ferric hydroxide was substituted in the place of precipitated manganese dioxide no inversion took place.

The individual products of the reaction between sulphur dioxide and manganese dioxide in water are manganese dithionate and manganese sulphate. A little sulphuric acid might also be formed by the oxidation of sulphurous acid. With a view to test whether any of these substances (manganese dithionate, dithionic acid, manganous sulphate and dilute sulphuric acid) has any influence on the inversion, the following experiments were performed, when it was found that these substances individually have no influence on the change.

Action of Manganous Sulphate.—A solution of 5 g. of manganous sulphate was added to a solution of 1.7 g. of maleic acid dissolved in 10 c.c. of water. The temperature of the mixture was maintained at 70° in a water-bath even for an hour but no fumaric acid separated on cooling, or when the solution was kept overnight. This proves that manganous sulphate itself has no influence on the inversion of maleic to fumaric acid.

Manganous Sulphate and Sulphur Dioxide.—A mixture of maleic acid and manganous sulphate solutions (saturated with sulphur dioxide) was heated at 70° for some time but no inversion occurred.

As a solution of sulphur dioxide is partially converted into sulphuric acid when boiled for some time, we thought that the presence of manganous sulphate which is a good oxidising catalyst might facilitate the oxidation of sulphurous to sulphuric acid and the latter might produce inversion, but the negative result obtained here with manganous sulphate and sulphur dioxide shows conclusively that the dilute sulphuric acid solution which might have been formed, has no influence on the inversion. In fact Skraup (*Monatsh.*, 11, 323) has shown that strong sulphuric acid produces inversion to some extent but the dilute acid does not and often retards it.

Manganese Dithionate.—A clear solution of manganese dithionate was added to a strong solution of maleic acid. No fumaric acid separated on warming for half an hour on the water-bath or when kept overnight.

Dithionic Acid.—A solution of dithionic acid (prepared by the careful addition of dilute sulphuric acid to a concentrated solution of barium dithionate and subsequent filtration) was added to a strong solution of maleic acid and shaken well. No fumaric acid was obtained even when kept overnight.

Action of Water and Sulphur Trioxide.—With a view to test if the formation of sulphuric acid by the action of water on sulphur trioxide is accompanied with inversion, sulphur trioxide crystals were added to a solution of 2.2 g. of maleic acid in 20 c.c. of water. A large amount of heat and fumes were evolved, but no fumaric acid separated, even after being kept at 70° for some time in a water-bath. P. Neogi, Chatterji and S. Neogi (*loc. cit.*) have already shown that such a highly exothermic reaction as the action of water on phosphorus pentoxide does not produce inversion. It would thus be seen that all exothermic reactions do not produce inversion.

Inversion of Methyl Maleate.—In the case of substances insoluble in water aqueous alcoholic solutions are taken. Methyl maleate (3.51 g.) was dissolved in 25 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 25 c.c. of water were added to it, followed by precipitated manganese dioxide (5 g.). A current of sulphur dioxide was passed through it till a clear solution was obtained. The excess of alcohol was evaporated away, when silky shining crystals were obtained. These were collected and crystallised from ether when methyl fumarate, m.p. 101°-102° was obtained (yield, 30-32%).

Inversion of Ethyl Maleate.—Ethyl maleate (4.2 g.) was treated similarly with manganese dioxide and sulphur dioxide. The oily

residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after evaporation and drying was fractionally distilled when ethyl fumarate came over at 216°-218°.

Inversion of Citraconic Acid.—Citraconic acid (2.8 g.) was dissolved in 10 c.c. of water and precipitated manganese dioxide (4.5 g.) was added to it. A current of sulphur dioxide was passed through the solution, until it became clear; the temperature rose to about 65°-70°. The solution after filtration was concentrated in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. After 2-3 days, crystals separated. These were filtered and dissolved in ether. The ethereal solution when allowed to evaporate, gave sparingly soluble crystals of mesaconic acid, m.p. 202° (yield, 20%). That the substance was mesaconic acid was conclusively proved by its action with ferric chloride, when a reddish solution was obtained which on warming and then allowing to cool, turned to a brown jelly-like substance. When the inversion was effected at 100°, the yield increased to 25%. It would thus appear that the inversion of citraconic to mesaconic acid is effected with greater difficulty than that of maleic to fumaric acid. The products of the reaction of sulphur dioxide and manganese dioxide failed to produce inversion in citraconic acid or esters of maleic acid.

It is further to be noted that in all cases the inversion is only partial, the percentage varying in different cases.

Action of Sulphur Dioxide and Manganese Dioxide on Erucic Acid and Oleic Acid.—Attempts were then made to apply this method to the inversion of more complex substances such as erucic and oleic acids. In all these cases however the results were negative.

Resonance Reactions.

It has conclusively been shown in the foregoing pages that maleic acid and its esters as well as citraconic acid undergo inversion in the midst of the reaction between sulphurous acid and manganese dioxide and that the products of the latter reaction, either singly or jointly, have no effect on the transformation. We have therefore no hesitation in affirming that a chemical reaction can act as a catalyst in effecting chemical transformations. Skraup's experiment with the transformation of maleic acid in the presence of the combined action of sulphuretted hydrogen and sulphur dioxide hitherto remained an isolated one, but the addition of the present results

makes the supposition of a new kind of chemical reaction almost irresistible. It is to be noted that such reactions would be entirely different from what are called "induced reactions." In the latter there is a primary and a secondary reaction and an 'acceptor,' 'actor' and an 'inductor.' In the new reaction, both the reactions are primary and independent of each other and there are no acceptor, actor or inductor, and in fact no reagent common to the two reactions. The chemical reactions that take place in the transformation of maleic to fumaric acid in the presence of manganese dioxide and sulphur dioxide are the following:—

It will readily be seen that the two reactions are entirely different from the primary and secondary reactions of an "induced reaction."

We have taken the word 'resonance' from a paragraph in Skraup's writing and named this new kind of chemical reaction 'resonance reaction' which might be defined as a chemical reaction which takes place in the midst of another chemical reaction but not in the presence of any of the reactants singly nor in the presence of the products of the latter reaction.

Geometrical inversions have, up to this time, been the only instances of resonance reactions. Other kinds of reactions are being experimented upon.

Whether an exothermic reaction sets up vibrations or not as postulated by Skraup in effecting geometrical inversion, is in the words of Cohen "beyond reach of experimental proof or disproof" and is not relied on here. We simply maintain that the energy liberated by specific exothermic reactions causes geometrical inversion by activation of the labile isomer. This is the explanation we are at present offering to explain the effect of "resonance reaction". Further work on the subject is proceeding.

